

***In Silico* Design, Synthesis and Evaluation of Pyrimidine Scaffold Bearing 1,3,4-Oxadiazole Moiety as Possible COX Inhibitors through their Anti Inflammatory and Antioxidant Potential**

Sonia George¹, Surya P.S.², Gayathri Senbagam^{3*}

¹Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Sri Ramakrishna Institute of Paramedical Sciences, College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore-641044, Tamil Nadu, India.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Sri Ramakrishna Institute of Paramedical Sciences, College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore-641044, Tamil Nadu, India.

³Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Sri Ramakrishna Institute of Paramedical Sciences, College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore-641044, Tamil Nadu, India.

Affiliated to The Tamil Nadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University, Chennai-600032, Tamil Nadu, India.

ABSTRACT

The discovery of dual-functional agents with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties is critical for addressing the limitations of current therapies. In this study, a series of pyrimidine scaffold derivatives bearing a 1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety (POD 1–8) were designed, synthesized, and evaluated for their potential as dual cyclooxygenase (COX-1 and COX-2) inhibitors with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Computational approaches, including molecular docking and ADMET analysis, were employed to predict binding affinities and pharmacokinetic profiles. The derivatives were synthesized through a multi-step process, with structures confirmed using IR, NMR, and mass spectrometry. The anti-inflammatory activity of the compounds was assessed using protein denaturation method and antioxidant activity by nitric oxide inhibition and reducing power method. Among the synthesized compounds, POD-1 and POD-6 demonstrated significant binding energies with both COX-1 (PDB ID: 2OYE) and COX-2 (PDB ID: 4COX) enzymes comparable to standard drug, indicating strong inhibitory potential across isoforms. POD-6, POD-3, and POD-1 exhibited significant anti-inflammatory activity with IC₅₀ values at 61.51 ± 0.7954, 73.17 ± 1.7693, and 77.20 ± 0.5425 µg/mL, respectively. These compounds also demonstrated potent antioxidant activity, assessed through reducing power and nitric oxide (NO) inhibition methods. This study highlights the promising dual-action potential of pyrimidine-oxadiazole hybrids, particularly POD-6, POD-3, and POD-1, as effective COX-1/COX-2 inhibitors with additional antioxidant benefits.

Keywords: Pyrimidine, 1,3,4-oxadiazole, Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, *in silico*.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammation is a protective response of the body that involves numerous cellular and molecular mechanisms regulated by inflammatory mediators. Cyclooxygenase (COX) enzymes have garnered considerable attention as promising targets for novel drug discovery because of their essential function in prostaglandin biosynthesis. Therefore, COX inhibition is a promising approach for the pharmacological intervention in inflammation. Non-

Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) are widely used to manage pain, fever, and inflammation in disorders such as arthritis, lupus, and psoriasis. Conventional NSAIDs inhibit both COX-1 and COX-2, but COX-1 inhibition often leads to gastrointestinal side effects. Selective COX-2 inhibitors, or coxibs, were developed to overcome this issue; however, some (like rofecoxib and valdecoxib) were later withdrawn due to cardiovascular risks.^[1]

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Cyclooxygenase catalyzes a controlled free radical chain reaction and generate free radicals. Although ROS aid immune defense, excessive levels can trigger oxidative and inflammatory injury, including lipid peroxidation and DNA damage.^{[2][3]} Oxidative stress and inflammation are tightly connected processes that contribute to chronic conditions including diabetes, cancer, and atherosclerosis. Since ROS can amplify inflammation, compounds with both antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties may offer therapeutic benefits.^[4]

Heterocycles such as pyrimidine derivatives display anticancer, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory potential. Drugs including afloqualone, proquazone, eprizole, and tofacitinib highlight the therapeutic significance of the pyrimidine scaffold. Oxadiazoles, especially 1,3,4-oxadiazoles, also demonstrate powerful antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, often through inhibition of cyclooxygenase and 5-lipoxygenase enzymes.^[5]

Amira I. Sayed et al., (2022)^[6] synthesised novel pyrrolo pyrimidines and pyrrolo triazolo pyrimidines as promising antioxidant and anti-inflammatory agents. Sibghat Mansoor Rana et al., (2023)^[7] synthesised and evaluated 2,5-Disubstituted-1,3,4 oxadiazole derivatives as Antioxidant and Anti-Inflammatory agents, Computational Studies were performed.

The work focusses on oxidative stress and inflammation as they are key factors in chronic diseases and cancer development. Cyclooxygenase (COX) enzyme was chosen as it contributes to prostaglandin production and generates free radicals, making COX inhibition a valuable strategy to reduce inflammation and oxidative stress. Heterocyclic pharmacophores such as pyrimidine and oxadiazole exhibit notable anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities. In this study, pyrimidine-linked oxadiazole derivatives were synthesized and evaluated for their ability to inhibit COX and scavenge free radicals, aiming to develop compounds with combined anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Softwares and databases used

Experimental section involved four phases 1) *In silico* studies 2) Synthetic studies 3) Analytical studies 4) *In vitro* screening. Softwares and Databases used in *in silico* studies were RCSB Protein Data Bank (<https://www.rcsb.org>), Online Smiles Translator (<https://cactus.nci.nih.gov/translate/>), ACD Chem Sketch 2018 v2.5, Molinspiration, Schrodinger Maestro v13.1, Glide v2.6 QikProp.

PHASE I: *IN SILICO* STUDIES

Cyclooxygenase enzymes was chosen based upon literature reviews. The 3D structures of the COX-2 & 1 receptor PDB ID:(4COX & 2OYE) were retrieved from the RCSB Protein Data Bank for molecular docking studies. From various literature reviewed, Pyrimidine scaffold bearing 1,3,4 oxadiazole derivatives has been selected for anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant activity. Lead molecules which possess good ADME properties have been selected for docking against COX enzyme (PDB ID: 4COX & 2OYE). Molecular docking studies are used to determine the interaction between the target enzyme and a ligand molecule. The docking studies were performed using Schrodinger Maestro v13.1 and the standard used against the enzymes was eprizole. The binding energies of the designed compounds were compared to that of the standard.

PHASE II: SYNTHETIC STUDIES

Chemicals and reagents used

Urea, ethyl acetoacetate, benzaldehyde, hydrazine hydrate, cyanogen bromide, para dimethyl amino benzaldehyde, para chloro benzaldehyde, para nitro benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, para fluoro benzaldehyde, 3,4-dichloro benzaldehyde, 3,4,5-trimethoxy benzaldehyde Ethanol, Conc. HCl, Conc. H₂SO₄, glacial acetic acid. All the reagents and chemicals were procured from Sigma Aldrich, Loba Chemie, Himedia and further they were used without purification. For synthesis normal reflux condenser setup was used.

Melting point of the synthesised compounds were determined by using thiele's tube and silica gel slurry was prepared and poured on plates for TLC determinations.

Chemistry

STEP 1: Synthesis of ethyl 6-methyl-2-oxo-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (1)

Urea (0.1 mol), ethyl acetoacetate (0.15 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (0.15 mol) were mixed in ethanol

(25 mL). A catalytic amount of Conc. HCl was added to the mixture, which was then refluxed for three hours. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice and left overnight. Solid product was separated, filtered. [8][9]

STEP 2: Synthesis of 6-methyl-2-oxo-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carbohydrazide (2)

To 0.01 mol of ester in ethanol (20 mL), hydrazine

hydrate (0.01 mol) was added, followed by a catalytic amount of conc. H_2SO_4 (3 drops). The mixture was refluxed for two hours. Excess solvent was removed and on cooling, a solid was formed. [8]

STEP 3: Synthesis of 5-(5-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-6-methyl-4-phenyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3)

To 0.01 mol of hydrazide in absolute ethanol (25 mL), cyanogen bromide (0.01 mol, 1.05 g) was

then added and refluxed for four hours. The reaction mixture was cooled, neutralised with sodium bicarbonate and poured into crushed ice. The solid separated was filtered and dried. [8]

STEP 4: Synthesis of 5-[5-(benzylideneamino)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]-6-methyl-4-phenyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (4a-4h) To 0.01 mol of oxadiazole amine and benzaldehydes (0.01 mol) were

added and refluxed in ethanol in the presence of a catalytic amount of glacial acetic acid for four hours and cooled. The solid separated was filtered off and

crystallized. The other derivatives were prepared in the same manner.

COMPOUND CODE	R	COMPOUND CODE	R
POD-1	-Hydrogen	POD-5	-4-methoxy
POD-2	-4-dimethylamino	POD-6	-4-Fluoro
POD-3	-4-Chloro	POD-7	-3,4-Chloro
POD-4	-4-nitro	POD-8	-3,4,5 -trimethoxy

Table 1: List of derivatives prepared

PHASE III: ANALYTICAL STUDIES

UV spectra was recorded on JASCO V-530 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer, IR spectra was recorded on JASCO V-530 Spectrophotometer, MASS spectroscopy was recorded on JASCO V-530, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, SRIPMS, College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore. NMR spectra was recorded on 300 MHz BRUKER, Karunya Institute of Technology and Sciences, Coimbatore.

PHASE IV: *IN VITRO* BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION

In vitro biological activity for anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effect was performed at Department of Pharmacology, SRIPMS, COP, Coimbatore.

In Vitro anti inflammatory activity by protein denaturation method

The reaction mixture of about 0.5 ml of various concentrations were prepared, comprising 0.2 mL of egg albumin and 2mL of test solution of different

concentrations (10, 20, 40, 80, 160, 320, 640 µg/ml). The pH was adjusted to 6.3 using 1N HCl. After preparation, the mixtures were incubated at 37°C for 20 minutes, followed by heating at 70°C for 10 minutes. Upon cooling the samples, 2.5 mL of phosphate buffer saline (pH 6.3) was added to each test tube. Additionally, 0.05 mL of distilled water was used in place of test solution in the control test tube, while product control did not contain albumin. Subsequently, the absorbance was measured using spectrometer at 660nm and percentage inhibition of protein denaturation was calculated using the formula. (10)

***In Vitro* antioxidant assay**

a) Nitric oxide inhibition method

0.5 ml of test solution from each concentration (20, 40, 60, 80, 100 µg/ml) was taken in a test tube and added 0.5 ml of phosphate buffer solution. To this 2 ml of the 10 mM sodium nitroprusside solution was added. This reaction mixture was incubated for 150 minutes at 25° C in incubator. 1 ml of the above

solution was pipetted out and to this added 2 ml of the Griess Reagent. The mixture was allowed to stand for 5 minutes to complete diazotization. Added 2 ml of the naphthyl ethylene diamine HCl (0.1 %) and allowed to stand for 30 minutes in diffused light. The absorbance of the pink colored solution was measured at 540 nm using Jasco spectrophotometer. The absorbance of blank was first noted at 540 nm. Ascorbic acid was used as a reference standard. The various concentrations of ascorbic acid ranging from 20-100 µg/ml was prepared. And the same procedure was repeated with ascorbic acid instead of test solution. As a blank (control), the assay mixture similarly run in the absence of test solution was used. The absorbance of blank (control) and reference standard were measured at 540 nm. ⁽¹¹⁾

b) Reducing Power Method

2.5 ml of the test solution from each concentration (20, 40, 60, 80, 100 µg/ml) was taken in a test tube and to this added 2.5 ml of phosphate buffer and 2.5 ml potassium ferricyanide solution. The mixture was incubated at 50⁰ C for 20 minutes in incubator. To the above solution, 2.5 ml of trichloro acetic acid solution was added. From this mixture, 2.5 ml of the solution was pipetted out and added 2.5 ml of distilled water. 0.5 ml of ferric Chloride solution was added to this. After shaking, the mixture was left at room temperature for 5 minutes and the absorbance of prussian blue colored solution was measured at 700 nm using Jasco spectrophotometer. Ascorbic acid was

used as a reference standard. The various concentrations of ascorbic acid ranging from 20-100 µg/ml was prepared. And the same procedure was repeated with ascorbic acid instead of test solution. As a blank (control), the assay mixture similarly run in the absence of test solution was used. The absorbance of blank and reference standard were measured at 700 nm. ⁽¹²⁾

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

IN SILICO STUDIES

The Cyclooxygenase enzymes (PDB ID: 4COX & 2OYE) was selected as target to bind with lead molecules. From literature survey, both pyrimidine and oxadiazole nucleus found to possess anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activity. Hence, the present work have been focused on Pyrimidine scaffold bearing 1,3,4 oxadiazole moiety as lead molecules. The designed leads were optimized for their ADME properties using Molinspiration, Qikprop software. The lead compounds were found to be safe. For better oral absorption of the ligands the drug likeliness scores are constructed by getting information about solubility, diffusion, log P, molecular weight etc. One of the ideal methods for this is using Lipinski's rule of five with the molinspiration server and the results are tabulated below.

S.No	Compound Code	Molecular Weight	No.of H bond acceptors	No.of H bond donors	No.of rotatable bonds	Log P	nviolations
1.	POD-1	359.39	7	2	4	2.69	0
2.	POD-2	402.46	8	2	5	2.79	0
3.	POD-3	393.82	7	2	4	2.54	0
4.	POD-4	404.39	10	2	5	2.65	0
5.	POD-5	389.42	8	2	5	2.75	0
6.	POD-6	377.38	7	2	4	2.85	0
7.	POD-7	428.28	7	2	4	3.98	0
8.	POD-8	449.47	10	2	7	2.32	0

Table 2: Drug likeliness screening using molinspiration server

The absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADMET) profiles of the designed leads were predicted using the QikProp module of Schrödinger software. All compounds exhibited zero violations (#stars=0), indicating that their physicochemical descriptors fall within the acceptable range of 95% of known drugs. The predicted parameters, such as molecular weight, partition coefficient (QPlogPo/w), solubility (QPlogS) were found to be within acceptable ranges, suggesting a balanced hydrophilic-lipophilic profile, sufficient solubility for oral absorption (Table 3). Consistent with these findings, human oral absorption percentage

was predicted to high (>90%) for all compounds except POD-4 (68.79%). Importantly, none of the compounds displayed violations that would preclude further development, and predicted HERG inhibition risk values (QPlogHERG) were also within safe limits, suggesting minimal cardiotoxicity potential. These results demonstrate that the designed molecules not only possess drug-like characteristics but also show promising pharmacokinetic properties, supporting their progression to molecular docking and biological evaluation stages.

CODE	#stars	Dipole	QPlogPo/w	QPlogS	QPlogHERG	QPPCaco	QPPMD CK	Percent Human Oral absorption
POD-1	0	5.393	3.323	-5.409	-6.33	350.341	159.221	91.944
POD-2	0	0	3.526	-5.992	-6.185	319.298	144.027	92.414
POD-3	0	0	3.613	-5.828	-5.972	323.603	358.251	93.025
POD-4	0	0	2.38	-5.356	-6.063	36.236	13.707	68.789
POD-5	0	0	3.102	-5.064	-5.745	346.55	157.359	90.565
POD-6	0	0	3.707	-5.968	-6.275	326.924	267.725	93.657
POD-7	0	0	3.99	-6.375	-5.875	338.322	778.142	95.58
POD-8	0	6.503	3.731	-6.337	-6.34	388.767	178.177	95.145

Table 3: Drug likeliness screening using qikprop server

Most compounds exhibited acceptable drug likeness with favourable permeability and low predicted cardiotoxicity, supporting their potential as orally active anti-inflammatory and antioxidant agents. However, compound POD-4 showed comparatively lower permeability and moderate absorption, which may limit its bioavailability. Overall, other derivatives can be considered as promising candidates for further studies.

The lead compounds were docked with target enzymes using Schrodinger Maestro v13.1. The docking results of Cyclooxygenase-2 & 1 with eight designed lead molecules Pyrimidine scaffold bearing 1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety and standard eprizole are reported below. The active sites are presented in the snap shots and the binding energy was found to be more or less equivalent or lower when compared to the standards used in the docking studies.

Molecular docking studies

Compound Code	Binding affinity Kcal/mol	
	COX-2 (4COX)	COX-1 (2OYE)
POD-1	-9.844	-9.213
POD-2	-7.041	-6.217
POD-3	-7.996	-6.936
POD-4	-7.767	-7.020

POD-5	-7.383	-6.369
POD-6	-9.582	-9.390
POD-7	-7.459	-6.907
POD-8	-7.581	-7.611
Epirizole	-7.423	-7.629

TABLE 4: Docking results of novel pyrimidine scaffold bearing 1,3,4 oxadiazole derivatives POD-1 to 8 against Cyclooxygenase-2 (PDB ID 4COX) Cyclooxygenase-1 (PDB ID 2oye)

In comparison with the standard ligand epirizole (binding energy -7.423 kcal/mol), compounds POD-1 and POD-6 showed higher binding energy -9.844 kcal/mol and -9.582 kcal/mol. Figure 1 depicts the

2D and 3D binding mode of epirizole and compounds POD-1 and POD-6 at the active site region of Cyclooxygenase-2 protein (PDB ID: 4COX).

2D and 3D Binding mode of compound POD-1 at the active region of Cyclooxygenase-2 (PDB ID 4COX)

2D and 3D Binding mode of standard epirizole at the active region of Cyclooxygenase-2 (PDB ID 4COX)

Figure 1: Molecular docking studies at active site region of Cyclooxygenase-2 (PDB ID 4COX)

2D and 3D Binding mode of compound POD-6 at the active region of Cyclooxygenase-1 (PDB ID 2oye)

2D and 3D Binding mode of standard epirizole at the active region of Cyclooxygenase-1 (PDB ID 2oye)

Figure 2: Molecular docking studies at active site region of Cyclooxygenase-1 (PDB ID 2oye)

Among the docked compounds, POD-6 showed binding energy **-9.390** and interacted at Tyr 355, Tyr 385, Ser 530, when compared with standard epirizole **7.629**, interacted at Tyr 355, Trp 387, Ser 530. POD-1 showed binding energy **-9.213** with interactions at Tyr 355, Tyr 385, Ser 530. Almost all the compounds showed good binding energies and interacted with important amino acids Tyr 355, Ser 530. Thus, the newly designed derivatives showed good binding energies against target (PDB ID: 2OYE) when compared with the standard.

PHASE II: SYNTHETIC STUDIES

All the eight synthesized compounds POD 1 to POD 8, obtained through four steps were prepared in good yield and evaluated by their physical characterization (Melting point and TLC) and spectral characterization (UV, IR, NMR and MASS) data.

PHASE III ANALYTICAL STUDIES

The structures of synthesized compounds during the present investigation were established on the basis of chemical data IR, UV, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and MASS spectral data.

6-methyl-4-phenyl-5-{5-[(phenylmethylidene)amino]-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl}-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-one (4a) IR (KBr, ν , cm^{-1}): 3244 (N-H), 3116 (Ar-H), 2978 (aliphatic C-H), 1701 (C=O), 1648 (C=C), 1512 (C=N), 1313 (C-N), 1221 (C-O). ^1H NMR [300 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm,]: 9.16 (s, 1H, NH), 7.22-7.32 (m, 10H, Ar-H), 5.14 (s, 1H, CH), 2.25 (s, 3H, CH $_3$). ^{13}C NMR [300 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm,]: 165.8 (C=O), 152.6 (C=N), 126.7-128.8 (Ar-C), 54.4 (CH), 18.2 (CH $_3$). ESI-MS: $[\text{M}+1]^+$ m/z 361.25.

5-{5-[(4-(dimethylamino) phenyl) methylidene] amino}-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl}-6-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-one (**4b**) IR (KBr, v, cm⁻¹): 3241 (N-H), 3162 (Ar-H), 2902 (aliphatic C-H), 1725 (C=O), 1659 (C=C), 1519 (C=N), 1371 (C-N), 1230 (C-O).

5-{5-[(4-chlorophenyl) methylidene] amino}-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl}-6-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-one (**4c**) IR (KBr, v, cm⁻¹): 3247 (N-H), 3159 (Ar-H), 2974 (aliphatic C-H), 1724 (C=O), 1648 (C=C), 1548 (C=N), 1290 (C-N), 1092 (C-O), 758 (C-Cl).

6-methyl-5-{5-[(4-nitrophenyl) methylidene] amino}-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl}-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-one (**4d**) IR (KBr, v, cm⁻¹): 3246 (N-H), 3128 (Ar-H), 2978 (aliphatic C-H), 1724 (C=O), 1648 (C=C), 1605 (C=N), 1313 (C-N), 1221 (C-O) 1290 (C-NO₂).

5-{5-[(4-methoxyphenyl)methylidene] amino}-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl}-6-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-one (**4e**) IR (KBr, v, cm⁻¹): 3243 (N-H), 3198 (Ar-H), 2977 (aliphatic C-H), 1724 (C=O), 1648 (C=C), 1548 (C=N), 1291 (C-N), 1222 (C-O).

5-{5-[(4-fluorophenyl) methylidene] amino}-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl}-6-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-one (**4f**) IR (KBr, v, cm⁻¹):

3245 (N-H), 3116 (Ar-H), 2978 (aliphatic C-H), 1724 (C=O), 1648 (C=C), 1548 (C=N), 1341 (C-N), 1290 (C-O) 1221(C-F). ¹H NMR [300 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm,]: 9.15 (s, 1H), 7.05-7.75 (m, 9H), 5.08 (s, 1H), 2.23 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR [300 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm,]: 165.8 (C=O), 152.6 (C=N), 128 (Ar-C), 55.1 (CH), 18.3 (CH₃). ESI-MS: M⁺377 m/z

5-{5-[(3,4-dichlorophenyl) methylidene] amino}-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl}-6-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-one (**4g**) IR (KBr, v, cm⁻¹): 3200 (N-H), 3104 (Ar-H), 2926 (aliphatic C-H), 1724 (C=O), 1648 (C=C), 1529 (C=N), 1313 (C-N), 1221 (C-O) 758 (C-Cl).

6-methyl-4-phenyl-5-{5- [(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl) methylidene] amino}-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl}-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-one (**4h**) IR (KBr, v, cm⁻¹): 3248 (N-H), 3120 (Ar-H), 2990 (aliphatic C-H), 1725 (C=O), 1648 (C=C), 1548 (C=N), 1313 (C-N), 1221 (C-O) 1092 (C-O-C).

IN VITRO BIOLOGICAL SCREENING

ANTI INFLAMMATORY SCREENING BY PROTEIN DENATURATION METHOD

The synthesized compounds were evaluated for *in-vitro* anti-inflammatory activity by the protein denaturation method and results are shown.

COMP OUND CODE	Percentage inhibition							IC ₅₀ µg/ml
	Concentration µg/ml							
	10	20	40	80	160	320	640	
POD-1	15.8±1.9692	26.9±1.082	42.6±1.444	55.3±0.7179	59.3±0.2858	70.4±0.016	78.3±0.987	77.2±0.5425
POD-2	12.3±0.9656	20.7±0.8527	31.4±1.1927	42.9±0.7073	56.4±0.5761	61.4±0.8936	71.1±1.543	122.3±0.894 2
POD-3	19.2±0.5761	25.9±0.7891	42.2±0.9764	51.6±1.346	59.8±0.253	72.6±0.6195	77.2±1.342	73.17±1.769 3
POD-4	14.6±0.5100	25.4±0.8605	39.2±0.9095	56.3±1.8932	60.3±0.7698	68.5±0.4654	78.4±0.5984	83.09±0.975 8
POD-5	15.8±0.3241	26.9±0.5214	33.6±0.4547	48.9±1.2791	59.3±0.2858	70.4±0.9564	79.3±1.432	87.03±1.094 3
POD-6	20.3±0.5309	29.7±0.2042	45.3±0.5932	52.4±1.2791	61.1±1.3145	79.2±1.397	85.1±0.496	61.51±0.795 4
POD-7	18.3±0.3743	26.1±1.6208	30.4±1.3143	41.9±0.4681	58.9±0.9572	64.2±1.093	74.2±0.5412	90.6±0.5838

POD-8	15.4±1.0828	20.3±0.8701	29.0±0.652	47.6±0.8507	55.4±1.7596	63.0±0.5978	69.55±0.3851	96.8±0.6984
DICLOFENAC	23.6±0.6846	36.4±0.7594	45.6±0.8471	58.3±1.0861	65.7±1.3971	79.5±0.6942	90.4±0.8492	48.9±1.6894

TABLE 5: Inhibition of protein denaturation by different concentrations of novel pyrimidine scaffold bearing 1,3,4- oxadiazole derivatives and standard diclofenac

Figure 3: Inhibition of protein denaturation by different concentrations of novel Pyrimidine scaffold bearing 1,3,4 oxadiazole moiety.

In vitro anti-inflammatory activity was determined for the synthesized compounds, POD-1 to 8 at concentrations ranging from 10-640 µg/ml. an increase in the percentage inhibition of denaturation was observed for increase in concentration. Among the POD-1 to 8 derivatives, POD-6 (fluoro) was found to be more active and the IC_{50} was found to be 61.51 µg/ml. Other derivatives such as POD-1, POD-3 (Chloro), POD-4 (nitro) showed moderate activity with IC_{50} value ranges 77-83 µg/ml whereas POD-5 (methoxy), POD-7 (di chloro), POD-8 (trimethoxy) showed mild activity with IC_{50} value

ranges 87-90 µg/ml. The standard drug Diclofenac at concentration of 10 µg/ml has shown percentage inhibition 23.6 ±0.6846 and for 640 µg/ml the percentage inhibition was 90.4±0.8492 with IC_{50} of 48.9 ±1.6894 µg/ml.

ANTIOXIDANT SCREENING

NITRIC OXIDE INHIBITION METHOD: The synthesized compounds were evaluated for *in-vitro* antioxidant activity by nitric oxide inhibition method and results are shown

COMPOUND CODE	Absorbance					% INHIBITION					IC_{50} µg/ml
	20	40	60	80	100	20	40	60	80	100	
POD-1	0.6224	0.3966	0.3010	0.2304	0.1623	27	53.4	64.7	72.97	80.96	38.46
POD-2	0.6784	0.6027	0.4924	0.4026	0.4020	20.44	33.98	42.25	52.78	52.85	80.80
POD-3	0.6045	0.4010	0.3010	0.2102	0.1624	29.1	52.97	64.7	75.34	80.95	37.39
POD-4	0.6115	0.4925	0.2884	0.2892	0.1720	28.28	42.24	66.17	66.08	79.82	42.97
POD-5	0.6996	0.5371	0.3922	0.3060	0.2212	17.95	37.01	53.18	64.11	74.05	54.61
POD-6	0.6021	0.4523	0.2996	0.2268	0.1425	29.38	46.45	64.86	73.4	83.28	41.65
POD-7	0.7002	0.6274	0.4012	0.3688	0.2682	17.88	26.4	52.94	56.74	68.54	63.21
POD-8	0.6872	0.6672	0.6224	0.5374	0.4523	19.4	21.75	27	36.97	46.35	140.9
Ascorbic acid	0.6127	0.4885	0.3322	0.2322	0.1722	28.14	42.71	61.04	72.76	79.8	43.05

Table 6: Antioxidant effect of novel pyrimidine scaffold bearing 1,3,4- oxadiazole derivatives against sodium nitroprusside induced nitric oxide production

Figure 4: Antioxidant effect of novel Pyrimidine scaffold bearing 1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety against sodium nitroprusside induced NO production

In vitro antioxidant activity was determined for the synthesized compounds, POD-1 to 8 at concentrations ranging from 20-100 µg/ml. An increase in the percentage inhibition was observed for increase in concentration.

In nitric oxide inhibition method, among the POD-1 to 8 derivatives, POD-3 (chloro) was found to be more active and the IC_{50} was found to be 37.31 µg/ml. POD-1, POD-4 (nitro), POD-5 (methoxy), POD-6 (fluoro) showed good to moderate activity with IC_{50} value ranges 38-54 µg/ml whereas POD-2(dimethyl

amino), POD-8(trimethoxy) showed mild activity with IC_{50} ranges from 80-140 µg/ml. The standard ascorbic acid at concentration of 20 µg/ml has shown percentage inhibition 23.6 ± 0.6846 and for 100 µg/ml the percentage inhibition was 79.8 with IC_{50} of 43.05 µg/ml.

REDUCING POWER METHOD

The synthesized compounds were evaluated for *in-vitro* antioxidant activity by reducing power method and results are shown

COMPOUND CODE	Absorbance					% INHIBITION					IC_{50} µg/ml
	20	40	60	80	100	20	40	60	80	100	
POD-1	0.5481	0.6284	0.7234	0.8026	0.8222	40.41	48.02	54.85	59.30	60.27	42.82
POD-2	0.4392	0.4829	0.5120	0.5424	0.6176	25.63	32.36	36.21	39.78	47.11	147.1
POD-3	0.5624	0.6382	0.7210	0.8188	0.8296	41.92	48.82	54.7	60.11	60.63	43.65
POD-4	0.5792	0.6304	0.7112	0.7996	0.8335	43.61	48.19	54.07	59.15	60.81	45.87
POD-5	0.4624	0.4728	0.5463	0.6176	0.6326	29.36	30.92	40.21	47.11	48.37	113.5
POD-6	0.5786	0.6123	0.7228	0.8124	0.8299	43.55	46.66	54.81	59.82	60.64	49.05
POD-7	0.4265	0.4786	0.5307	0.5926	0.6125	23.42	31.75	30.45	44.88	46.67	130.9
POD-8	0.4828	0.5932	0.6147	0.6676	0.6920	32.35	44.94	46.86	51.07	52.80	74.27
Ascorbic acid	0.5380	0.6086	0.7135	0.7824	0.8050	39.2	46.33	55.15	58.25	60.67	45.50

Table 7: Antioxidant activity of novel pyrimidine scaffold bearing 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives by reducing power method

Figure 5: Antioxidant activity of novel Pyrimidine scaffold bearing 1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety by reducing power method

In reducing power method, among the POD-1 to 8 derivatives, POD-1 and 3 (chloro) was found to be more active and the IC_{50} was found to be 42.82 and 43.65 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. POD- 4 (nitro), POD-6 (fluoro), POD-8 (trimethoxy) showed good activity with IC_{50} value ranges from 45-74 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ whereas POD-2 (dimethyl amino), POD-5 (methoxy), POD-7(di chloro) with IC_{50} ranges from 113-147 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

The standard ascorbic acid at concentration of 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ has shown percentage inhibition 39.2 and for 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ the percentage inhibition was 60.67 with IC_{50} of 45.50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

All the newly synthesized compounds were tested for their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activity. Almost all the synthesized analogues showed significant inhibitory activity by protein denaturation assay, nitric oxide inhibition, reducing power and there was a dose dependent increase in the percentage inhibition for all concentrations.

CONCLUSION

The present work utilized computational tools in target selection, designing lead compounds, determining the binding affinities of the leads which enables *in silico* screening prior to synthetic studies, thus minimizing the tedious process of drug discovery. The *in-silico* ADME, drug-likeness scores of the ligands showed the compounds were orally bioactive drug. The binding energy obtained from the docking study further confirmed the affinity of the designed leads towards the enzymes

Cyclooxygenases. Various pyrimidine linked oxadiazoles were synthesised in good yield. The structures of the synthesised molecules were confirmed by physicochemical parameters and spectral analysis. The compounds were screened for anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activity. Thus, the present study includes *in silico* design, synthesis and evaluation of Pyrimidine scaffold bearing 1,3,4-oxadiazole moiety as possible COX inhibitors through their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant potential. Among the synthesised compounds chloro, fluoro, nitro substituted pyrimidine linked oxadiazole derivatives were found to be potent inhibitor due to superior docking and biological activity results.

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Conflicts of Interest- The author declares there is no conflict of Interest.

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